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SYSTEM OF CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF BIOCLIMATIC MODELING OF DESIGN OBJECTS

Abstract

The study presents a comprehensive system of criteria and indicators for assessing the effectiveness of bioclimatic modeling of design objects. The relevance of the work is due to the need to create a scientifically sound methodology for evaluating bioclimatic modeling solutions in the context of modern environmental challenges and the development of sustainable design. The purpose of the study is to develop a system of criteria for evaluating options for bioclimatic modeling of design objects with the definition of appropriate indicators for each criterion. The research methodology is based on a systematic approach to the analysis of bioclimatic modeling, expert assessments and multi-criteria analysis. The result of the study is the development of a five-criteria evaluation system: climate adaptation (C_1), environmental sustainability (C_2), energy efficiency (C_3), aesthetics and functionality (C_4), innovation (C_5). Each criterion is detailed with appropriate indicators that allow for both qualitative and quantitative assessment of bioclimatic solutions. The practical significance of the work lies in the possibility of using the proposed system to develop more sustainable, ecological, energy-efficient and innovative solutions in bioclimatic modeling of design objects of various types. The scientific novelty of the research lies in the creation of a comprehensive multi-level system for evaluating bioclimatic modeling, which takes into account the specifics of various types of design objects and provides a systematic approach to assessing their bioclimatic characteristics.

Keywords : Bioclimatic modeling, evaluation criteria, design objects, environmental sustainability, energy efficiency, climate adaptation.

Introduction

Modern global environmental challenges and climate change actualize the need for the development and implementation of bioclimatic approaches in design activities. Traditional methods of designing design objects often do not take into account the interaction with natural and climatic conditions, which leads to inefficient use of resources and negative impact on the environment. Bioclimatic modeling as an innovative approach to creating design objects requires scientifically based criteria for assessing the effectiveness of decisions made [2].

The relevance of the research is confirmed by the growing interest in bioclimatic architecture and the need to extend its principles to other areas of design, including industrial, graphic and environmental design. The connection of the problem with important scientific tasks is the development of methodological foundations for assessing and improving the effectiveness of bioclimatic solutions in design, which is also noted in [1].

Analysis of modern research indicates the active development of scientific directions of bioclimatic project activities and ecological design. A significant contribution to the development of theoretical foundations of bioclimatic modeling is research on the development of expert systems and decision support, where conceptual principles for creating a hybrid

knowledge base for bioclimatic modeling are proposed [2].

A study of criteria for assessing the environmental sustainability of construction projects in [4] demonstrates the development of multi-criteria approaches to assessing environmental indicators, including energy, emissions, waste, materials, water and land resources. The authors group the criteria into categories: environmental management, resource consumption and protection, design, policies and certification, and conservation.

As noted in [6], the principles of sustainable design define six fundamental areas: optimizing site potential, optimizing energy use, protecting and conserving water, optimizing the use of building space and materials, improving the quality of the indoor environment, and optimizing operational and technical practices.

In the study [3], a three-level criteria structure is proposed as a method for evaluating ecological buildings: environmental protection, resource efficiency, and user comfort and health. Each category includes specific indicators and a system of weighting factors.

The authors in [5] explore how ecodesign can help improve environmental impact assessment (EAM) methods used by higher education institutions. The proposed method integrates ecodesign tools, such as life cycle assessment (LCA), environmental

benchmarking, and parametric design tools, with existing EAM frameworks.

An unresolved part of the problem is the lack of an adapted system of bioclimatic modeling criteria for different types of design objects (industrial, graphic, environmental design), which would take into account the specifics of interaction with climatic conditions and provide a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of bioclimatic solutions.

The purpose of the study is to develop and scientifically and theoretically substantiate a comprehensive system of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of bioclimatic modeling of design objects with the definition of relevant indicators to ensure an objective assessment of the quality and effectiveness of bioclimatic solutions in various areas of design.

Presentation of the main material.

Theoretical foundations of the formation of a system of criteria

In the process of bioclimatic modeling, there is a need to compare and evaluate the options for the developed solutions. The evaluation criterion is defined as a system of the most significant features that reflects not the entire object under study, but only those aspects of it that meet the purpose of the study and are subject to qualitative and quantitative interpretation. Each criterion includes a set of indicators that define it both qualitatively and quantitatively. The quality of bioclimatic modeling of a design object represents a set of properties that allow satisfying the predetermined needs of users in accordance with the purpose of the design object, taking into account the influence of natural and climatic parameters. Effectiveness is defined as the ability of the proposed bioclimatic modeling solution to achieve the set goals with the required level of quality and effectiveness.

Structure of the five-criteria evaluation system.

The proposed system of criteria includes five main criteria:

- C_1 – Climate adaptation;
- C_2 – Environmental sustainability;
- C_3 – Energy efficiency;
- C_4 – Aesthetics and functionality;
- C_5 – Innovation.

Each of the criteria is detailed by the corresponding indicators, let's consider them in more detail.

Criterion C_1 : Climate adaptation is the basis of bioclimatic modeling and involves taking into account the impact and change of climate to adapt design objects to the natural and climatic conditions of the environment. It is proposed to consider groups of indicators, each of which covers a certain aspect of the interaction of the object with climatic conditions.

Indicators $I_1^1 - I_1^3$ of criterion C_1 allow to assess the adaptation of design objects to the climate at different levels: macroclimate, mesoclimate, microclimate. An example of application is bioclimatic modeling of clothing design, which involves the creation of models that provide optimal human comfort in changing climatic conditions at the microlevel. Thus, indicator I_1^3 includes an analysis of climatic parameters:

- Air temperature: ensuring thermal comfort at a given external temperature, taking into account changes in body surface temperature and the rate of sweat evaporation;
- Air humidity: ensuring the drying speed of clothing fabric, the ability to absorb moisture to form a dry microclimate at a given level of external humidity;
- Wind regime: ensuring ventilation, preventing overheating, air permeability under different wind regimes.

Indicator I_1^4 characterizes the dynamic processes of "Adaptive capacity" - the ability of a design object to change its characteristics depending on changes in climatic conditions.

Criterion C_2 : Environmental sustainability in the context of bioclimatic modeling involves assessing the compliance of a design object with the principles of environmental conservation. This includes reducing negative environmental impact, reducing emissions of harmful substances, and forming environmentally sustainable design solutions.

The system of indicators I_2 of criterion C_2 includes:

I_2^1 – *material use* : determines the content of recycled materials, local origin of materials, resource efficiency of materials.

I_2^2 – *impact on biodiversity* : determines the preservation of green spaces, the use of local species of flora and fauna, and the creation of conditions for biodiversity.

I_2^3 – *waste management* : determines the percentage of recycled materials used, waste reduction measures, and recycling rate.

I_2^4 – *emissions of pollutants* : determines the volume of CO2 emissions, the level of wastewater pollution, the use of treatment systems.

The choice of these indicators is due to the possibility of a comprehensive assessment of the environmental sustainability of a design object during bioclimatic modeling, taking into account both direct and indirect impacts on the environment.

Criterion C_3 : Energy efficiency. Bioclimatic modeling should contribute to optimizing the energy consumption of design objects. Expanding the use of bioclimatic modeling to various types of design will allow increasing the energy efficiency not only of buildings, but also of other industrial, graphic, and environmental design objects.

For criterion C_3 , a system of indicators I_3 is proposed, which includes:

General indicators I_3^{common} for all types of design objects:

- Use of renewable energy sources;
- Energy footprint of design objects throughout their life cycle (production, transportation, use, disposal).

Specialized indicators for specific types of design objects:

- I_3^f (furniture): level of energy and resource efficiency of production and operation, Circular Design, effective packaging and logistics solutions;
- I_3^{tons} (transport): specific fuel or energy consumption, aerodynamic efficiency, energy recovery efficiency;

- I_3^{units} (clothing): thermal insulation properties, hygroscopicity, energy consumption during production, impact on the body's microclimate;

- I_3^{gr} (graphic design): choosing paper and printing inks with a low energy footprint; optimizing the amount of printed products; using electronic formats instead of printed ones.

- I_3^{arch} (architectural objects): annual primary energy consumption, specific energy consumption, amount of energy consumed per unit area or volume of the object, energy balance.

Criterion C4: Aesthetics and functionality. The bioclimatic modeling process allows designers to create objects that harmoniously combine aesthetics and functionality, taking into account natural conditions and climatic features. Nature is an inexhaustible source of inspiration for bioclimatic design solutions, providing numerous examples of unique structures adapted to natural and climatic environmental conditions. The formation of design objects in bioclimatic modeling is determined by the interaction of structural-functional, nature-oriented and artistic-figurative means of thinking.

The system of indicators I_4 includes:

I_4^1 – *Volumetric-spatial indicators* : formation of volume, size, location of an object in space to ensure functionality, aesthetic perception, and effective interaction with the environment.

I_4^2 – *Artistic and figurative indicators* : formation of a bioclimatic style using organic forms, reproduction of natural analogues, use of elements of traditional national culture.

I_4^3 – *Compositional indicators* : analysis of scale, stylistic unity, metro-rhythmic patterns, compositional accents taking into account the optimal use of natural resources.

I_4^4 – *Structural indicators*: assessment of materials (environmental friendliness, strength, ability to self-regulate), texture, division of elements, means of transformation.

I_4^5 – *Color and light indicators* : forming harmony of light and shade distribution and coloristic solutions through the analysis of psycho-emotional perception, visual perception of form, informative and communicative perception.

Criterion C5: Innovativeness involves assessing the expansion of the use of bioclimatic modeling to various types of design, which contributes to the development of innovative approaches and new technologies. The set of indicators I_5 allows for quantitative and qualitative assessment of the level of innovativeness:

I_5^1 – *Level of innovation of the design concept* : originality of design, creativity of solutions for the implementation of bioclimatic modeling, potential for development, possibility of scaling.

I_5^2 – *Level of technological novelty*: quantitative indicators (number of patents) and qualitative indicators (level of automation, introduction of new materials and technologies).

I_5^3 – *Optimization of the modeling process*: quantitative indicators (reduction in the number of iterations, reduction in prototyping costs) and

qualitative indicators (quality of decisions made, level of collaboration between specialists).

The use of the evaluation criteria system allows developing more sustainable, ecological, energy-efficient and innovative solutions in bioclimatic modeling of design objects. The use of evaluation criteria indicators allows not only to measure efficiency, but also to identify key factors affecting bioclimatic indicators. The advantage of the proposed system is its versatility and adaptability to different types of design objects while maintaining a comprehensive approach to assessing bioclimatic characteristics. The system provides a transition to a systematic analysis of the success of implemented solutions and a systematic approach to assessing bioclimatic design objects.

Conclusions. The proposed system of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of bioclimatic modeling of design objects represents a comprehensive scientifically based approach to assessing the quality and effectiveness of bioclimatic solutions. The scientific novelty of the study lies in the creation of a five-criteria system (climate adaptation, environmental sustainability, energy efficiency, aesthetics and functionality, innovation), which takes into account the specifics of different types of design objects and provides a multi-level assessment of bioclimatic characteristics. Each criterion is detailed by a system of indicators that allow for both qualitative and quantitative assessment of bioclimatic solutions. A feature of the developed system is its adaptability to various design industries - from architectural objects to industrial design, clothing design and graphic design.

The practical significance of the research results lies in the possibility of applying the proposed system of criteria to increase the effectiveness of bioclimatic modeling in design practice, which will contribute to the development of more sustainable and environmentally responsible design solutions. The proposed system of criteria provides a systematic approach to the assessment of bioclimatic design objects and allows moving on to a systematic analysis of the success of implemented solutions. Prospects for further research include the development of models for quantitative assessment of criteria and the creation of automated decision support systems in bioclimatic modeling.

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